

Radiated Emission & Susceptibility EMI Testing: The Advantages Of Conducting Unit Level Tests In A System Level Environment

by

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Abstract

After twenty years of conducting EMC analyses, predictions and fix-it efforts for various Naval systems and platforms, I have concluded that a tremendous amount of time and money could be saved and more meaningful EMI test results could be obtained, if existing MIL-STD EMI test procedures could be modified to permit cabinet (unit) level testing to be conducted while having the total system electronics inter-connected in a system level environment.

This paper proposes a concept where electronic systems consisting of more than one cabinet could be EMI tested while configured and operating in a system level, "test bed" type of environment. This would require the development of a portable electromagnetically isolated, test chamber. This chamber will have built in near field measurement sensors that would permit the chamber to be utilized in an oversized system development laboratory which has been peripherally shielded with copper screening.

Development of this capability would provide the government with significant cost savings associated with: (1) reducing system movements and re-configurations, (2) reducing the need for special test cables, dummy loads and simulators, and (3) reducing EMI test times for the system, which would ultimately reduce the total time required to develop, test and ship new electronic systems for shipboard use.

Background

Even with the high number of reported EMI problems occurring on U.S. Naval platforms, it is not uncommon to have MIL-STD EMI qualification testing on new systems either eliminated or significantly reduced in scope due to; pressing shipboard installation schedules, the high cost of conducting the EMI tests and the more austere system development budgets of recent years.

When an electronic system is equal or smaller than one cabinet in size, it is relatively easy to conduct MIL-STD EMI qualification tests [1]. However, many of today's electronic systems consist of more than one cabinet, with the larger systems having a total of forty or more cabinets spread throughout the ship. For these systems it is much more difficult for EMI test personnel to conduct meaningful EMI tests on each cabinet, while still maintaining the system level intra and inter-connections (electrical) vital to ensuring proper system operations during the EMI tests.

Disadvantages Of Unit Level Testing

Unit level EMI tests are conducted to ensure that the EMI testing measures radiated and conducted emissions and susceptibility from only the Equipment Under Test (EUT) and not from other units or even the measurement equipment. Since the MIL-STD-461 radiated emission limits are low, it also means that electromagnetic shielding is required to reduce the potentially high factory EM environment. Unless the testing is being accomplished in an unusually high level EM area, copper screening should offer sufficient protection for most unit or system level EMI testing.

Unit level EMI testing has been shown to be a very expensive way to conduct EMI testing. A recent example of a required EMI radiated emission re-test (two, H field & two, E field tests) for nine cabinets was estimated to cost over \$500,000. The complete system consisted of thirty-four cabinets; can you imagine what the cost would be to conduct all of the required MIL-STD-462 tests on all of the cabinets? The \$500,000 cost discussed above includes many costs not associated with the actual EMI testing. Some of the extra costs associated with unit level EMI testing are:

- a. cost to develop and construct (often) unrealistic simulators to drive and/or load individual units (cabinets), because other system cabinets are not present during unit level testing,
- b. cost to develop and construct dummy loads for the system front-end and/or the systems outputs because of shipboard interfaces that are not present during unit level testing,
- c. cost to individually move each unit to-and-from the EMI test facility which may not even be located at the same site as the production or system test facilities,
- d. cost for additional cables, connectors and labor to fabricate the inter-connection cables required for each unit undergoing EMI testing,
- e. cost and delay associated with removing each unit from early pre-production or production runs to fit into the unit level EMI test schedule,

- f. cost and delay associated with setting up each particular EMI test for each unit moved into the unit level EMI test area,

Other Negative Factors Associated With Unit Level Testing

Input Simulations/Dummy Loads: In addition to the extra costs discussed above, what is not often considered is the fact that during unit level EMI testing each EUT is connected to specially made system simulators and terminated by dummy loads. These simulators can be poor and (often) unrealistic representations of what the actual system would "see" if the unit were configured at either the system test site or the shipboard installation. These improper loads significantly affect the emission and susceptibility characteristics of the EUT. In fact, it is widely known that at least a few cabinet level tests have been conducted on individual cabinets that did not even have cables connected; talk about unrealistic test conditions!

Shielded Room Measurement Problems: Conducting unit level EMI tests in shielded enclosures permits the EMI test organization to provide a high degree of confidence that their EMI tests are completed on time without being effected by EM emissions associated with outside environments, other equipments or their own test equipment. However, unless the EMI test facility is capable of testing very large objects, such as an entire airplane, etc, the characteristics of the more typical smaller, non-anechoic EMI shielded room can have a significant impact on the accuracy and repeatability of the EMI emissions testing. Mr. M. L. Crawford has measured [2] up to 30 dB of electric field measurement errors associated with reflections and resonances within smaller EMI shielded rooms without anechoic absorbent material.

Cable Emissions: When individual cabinet radiated emissions are measured in a typical EMI shielded room, cable emissions associated with excessive lengths of exposed cable have been known to dominate the radiated emission of the EUT. If this same unit were located in a system test bed a high percentage of these same cables would in all likelihood be placed beneath a metallic raised floor. This metallic floor could then reduce the effect of the cable radiation within the shielded system-test-bed enclosure.

PREFERRED SYSTEM CONFIGURATION FOR EMI TESTING

I have spent a number of years participating in, conducting, monitoring and/or providing EMC recommendations on MIL-STD EMI testing for equipment to be installed on various Naval platforms. I believe the following topics, stated as recommendations, are significant in determining whether the MIL-STD EMI testing produces results that can be related to achieving shipboard EMC:

- a. system front-end cabinets must have their sensor inputs properly dummy loaded with multi terminal impedances. These dummy loads will provide realistic impedances that will permit common mode-to-differential mode EMI conversion to occur due to inherent system imbalances,
- b. all cabinets should be inter-connected with each other in a normal manner utilizing the system cables that are to be installed on the platform,
- c. for all susceptibility tests the probability of the system being affected by EMI will be enhanced by:
 - (1) utilizing the maximum amount of actual system signal processing ,
 - (2) utilizing the system outputs as the primary susceptibility detection criterion to signify disrupted system operation, and
 - (3) utilizing low frequency modulation for all of the radiation susceptibility sources,
- d. the entire system should be configured in a system level environment and it shall be operating in either a normal or diagnostic test mode that will verify its design performance requirements or minimum detectable signal (MDS) capability (front-end to system output) both prior to and during the EMI testing, and then
- e. the emission or susceptibility of each cabinet should be evaluated in this system level environment while electromagnetically isolating each unit-under-test from all other system units (all system units are of course still electrically inter-connected),

The testing discussed above can then be compared and related to EMI and/or system performance (MDS) testing accomplished onboard Naval platforms. At the present time MIL-STD EMI testing has very little usefulness to aid in predicting whether a system will either produce EMI or respond to EMI after it is installed on a platform. The system level testing proposed herein, will provide the connection between unit level EMI testing and shipboard EMI/performance testing.

CONDUCTED EMISSION & MAGNETIC FIELD TESTING IN A SYSTEMS LEVEL FACILITY

Conducted Emissions Measurements: With proper attention provided during the modification of the systems test bed facility an electronic systems powerline conducted emissions can be tested accurately and in some cases easier than in a unit level test facility. Larger systems often have power distribution units that supply a.c. or d.c. power to more than one cabinet. The conducted emission (CE) or conducted susceptibility (CS) of more than one cabinet can then be measured simultaneously. From an EMI viewpoint this is a more realistic test of an equipments

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SUMMARY

emission and susceptibility. Some systems may not respond to a single unit CS source but may respond when multiple units are simultaneously stimulated, just as they would be stimulated on a ship.

Radiated Magnetic Field Measurements: The amplitude of most magnetic field sources falls-off as a function of distance from the source, at a rate between $1/r$ and $1/r^3$. Therefore when systems cabinets are separated by at least one meter, in order to perform the EMI tests in the system level environment, then there should be a low probability of magnetic interaction between adjacent cabinets.

REQUIRED CHANGES TO PERMIT SYSTEM LEVEL EMI TESTING

Presently, due to the existing configurations and/or limitations of typical EMI test facilities and system test bed facilities, the type of testing discussed above would be difficult to implement. However, it is expected that with very little additional expense these two functions (system test & EMI test) could be completed in one facility which would be slightly larger than the existing system level test bed facility. This would require the following changes to the system test bed facility:

- a. a larger area is needed since a separation of at least one meter will be required around each cabinet to permit the portable EM isolation test chamber to be installed around each cabinet,
- b. copper screening, or other shielding material, will need to be applied around the perimeter of this test area to provide shielding against external EM fields,
- c. a.c. and d.c. power into this area will have to be either supplied by separate generators or it will have to be filtered/conditioned to isolate the conducted emissions of sources inside and outside, of this area, and
- d. development of the portable EM isolation test chamber and near field antenna(s)/probe(s) must be initiated.

CONCEPTUAL DRAWING OF SYSTEM LEVEL TEST FACILITY

Figure (1) provides an example of various electronic equipment that could be inter-connected in one particular below decks shipboard compartment. A system level EMI test would have to evaluate all of the equipment that would be grouped into one compartment. Figure (2) illustrates how the portable EM isolation test chamber would appear when utilized in an oversized system test bed facility.

It is believed that providing the additional spatial separation between system cabinets, combined with the development and utilization of a portable electromagnetically isolating enclosure, with built in near field sensors, will permit the utilization of a system level EMI test facility. The system level EMI tests conducted within this facility will have acceptable measurement accuracy without incurring the tremendously high costs and improper cabinet stimulations associated with the present type of individual cabinet level EMI testing.

The goal of this paper is to stimulate various companies presently involved in conducting EMI measurements, to propose to the Navy various concepts to satisfy the isolation and near-field measurement requirements of this electromagnetically isolated portable test chamber. Development of this system test bed EMI measurements capability would permit a company's EMI measurement team, or an EMI "test-house" EMI measurement team, to go where the system is, as opposed to shipping the system to the EMI measurement laboratory. This would eliminate the system movements that significantly disrupt a systems development, evaluation and/or installation schedules.

It is anticipated that the cost savings associated with not conducting unit level EMI tests on one major combat system could pay for the one time costs of improving the system test bed facility.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that considerable cost savings could be achieved for multi-cabinet systems if a portable electromagnetic isolation chamber, with built in near field probes, could be utilized in a modified system test bed laboratory to conduct MIL-STD EMI tests.

The Navy should entertain proposals to evaluate the technical feasibility of utilizing this proposed concept. This would require support from the Navy to:

- a. develop and test a portable electromagnetic isolation chamber,
- b. develop and test near field passive probes that will provide a reasonable degree of measurement accuracy when used inside the EM isolation chamber, then either
- c. develop or modify active antennas for high level susceptibility tests conducted within the EM isolation chamber. Perhaps enclosure sides could be temporarily isolated or even a separate enclosure utilized to create parallel plate antennas for susceptibility testing, or
- d. evaluate the use of directional high level susceptibility test antennas that can be used within

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the entire system test bed facility that can be operated without use of the EM isolation chamber.

A large multi-cabinet electronic system, presently under development, should be selected for evaluation of the entire system test bed EMI measurement concept.

The Navy should consider developing a system level EMI test specification so that MIL-STD-462 can be utilized to do what it was designed to do; evaluate the EMI characteristics of small units.

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1. MIL-STD-462, "Electromagnetic Interference Characteristics, Measurement of "
2. M.L. Crawford, "Evaluation of Shielded Enclosure for EMI/EMC Measurements Without And With RF Anechoic Material". Paper published in the proceedings, 5th Symposium and Technical exhibition Of EMC, Zurich, March 8-10, 1983.

Figure (1)
Typical Shipboard Equipment Space

Figure (2)
Visualization of System Level EMI Test Facility with
Portable EM Isolation Test Chamber